

MODERN EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE GLAUCOMA ATTACKS COMORBID WITH NON-COMMUNICABLE CHRONIC DISEASES IN VALLEY CONDITIONS

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Relevance of the topic. The method of drug treatment of glaucoma, glaucomatous processes, and AGA has certain features, especially when it is accompanied by comorbid diseases. From the point of view of modern pharmacotherapy, their analysis and assessment are of undoubted interest and play an important role in the safety of this process.

As can be seen from the presented data, β -adrenoblockers, which are currently widely used (for hypotensive purposes), can worsen respiratory functions in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and in elderly patients (even in the absence of a history of COPD). In such cases, the drugs of choice in patients with glaucomatous COPD are prostaglandin analogues, local carbonic anhydrase inhibitors, and α 2-adrenomimetics.

Studies confirm that local medicines, which are used daily, for a long time, or for life, and often have a systemic effect, should certainly be considered from the point of view of safety.

Material and method. Modern epidemiological characteristics of the association of AGA with comorbidity of non-communicable chronic diseases (NCD) in the conditions of the valley were identified and assessed. It has been established that most AGA have comorbidity with cardiovascular diseases (CCVD), comorbidity with respiratory diseases (CRD), comorbidity with gastrointestinal diseases (CGD), comorbidity with diseases of the urinary system (CUD), and comorbidity with diabetes mellitus (CD).

The association of AH with AGA is confirmed by a difference in the frequency of occurrence in women and men - 61.2% and 38.8% [$\chi^2=0.025$; $P>0.05$; $p=-0.007$; 95%CI = 0.687-1.376]. The frequency of such association with IHD is -64% and 36% [$\chi^2=0.724$; $P>0.05$; $p=-0.037$; RR=0.840; 95%CI = 0.561-1.256].

Comorbidity of acute glaucoma attack with respiratory disease is mainly registered in the female and male populations with comorbidities of moderate diseases - chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), bronchial asthma (BA), and acute respiratory diseases (ARD). In particular, the frequency of COPD and COPD comorbidity was 64.5% in women and 35.5% in men, 95%CI=0.532-

2.283]. The same comorbidity with BA is observed - 50.0% and 50.0%, respectively [$\chi^2=4.011$; $P<0.05$; $p=0.086$; $RR=1.669$; $95\%CI = 1.007-2.764$].

In addition, it is noteworthy that the comorbidity of AGA with ARD was noted in 75.5% of women and 24.5% of men [$\chi^2=4.837$; $P<0.05$; $p=-0.095$; $RR=0.475$; $95\%CI = 0.242-0.934$].

The frequency of detecting comorbidity of PUD and AGA was recorded as 60.2% in women and 39.8% in men [$\chi^2=0.026$; $P>0.05$; $r=0.007$; $RR=1.037$; $95\%CI=0.668-1.609$].

The frequency of the clinical course of glaucoma attacks in association with tumor diseases in the female and male population is 54.5% and 45.5% respectively [$\chi^2=0.595$; $P>0.05$; $p=0.033$; $RR = 1.321$; $95\%CI=0.650-2.681$].

NCDG is mainly confirmed by glomerulonephritis and urolithiasis (STD) and comorbidity of AGA. The frequency of association of glomerulonephritis and GCC in women and men is characterized by 58.0% and 42.0% [$\chi^2=0.194$; $P>0.05$; $p=0.019$; $RR=1.142$; $95\%CI=0.633-2.061$]. In the conditions of the valley, the frequency of detection of GFC comorbidity with MCI was - 67.4% (in women) and 32.6% (in men).

The frequency of detection of CKD in the women's and men's populations corresponded to 57.3% and 47.7% with a significant difference [$\chi^2=0.637$; $P>0.05$; $p=0.037$; $RR=1.200$; $95\%CI=0.767-1.877$].

The identified results confirm, firstly, the predominance of comorbidity in GCC, and secondly, the fact that it is more frequently registered in women, and thirdly, the registration of comorbidities with the highest frequency represents a regional characteristic in valley conditions.

It is noted that the rural population has a higher frequency of glaucoma attacks against the background of comorbidity compared to the urban population, and more often, such a course is observed in rural women. This situation can be explained by the fact that medical supervision is higher compared to the urban population, and therefore, a sharp increase in the rate of further introduction of planned and emergency ophthalmological and preventive services into rural conditions, based on the implementation of Presidential decrees, and their improvement, is a priority scientific direction and a topic of practical importance.

Conclusion: It is noted that the rural population has a higher incidence of glaucoma attacks against the background of comorbidity compared to the urban population, and moreover, such a course is observed in rural women. This situation can be explained by the fact that medical supervision is higher

compared to the urban population, and therefore, a sharp increase in the rate of further introduction of planned and emergency ophthalmological and preventive services into rural conditions, based on the implementation of Presidential decrees, is a priority scientific direction and a topic of practical importance.

In the settled population, the frequency of comorbidity of noncommunicable chronic diseases in AGA reaches up to 100.0%, with high frequencies of detection, cases of comorbidity of glomerulonephritis and AGA are noted in the valley. The contribution of the total number of comorbidities to the recurrence of glaucoma attacks is very high - from 95.3% to 100.0%. Therefore, when determining measures for the prevention of AGA and emergency treatment, it is recommended to take into account such a characteristic course of the disease, so that the risk or catastrophe of AGA can be eliminated up to 100%.

In the population with an acute glaucoma attack, high frequencies of comorbidity of noncommunicable chronic diseases are observed in the age group >60 years and are mainly associated with comorbidity of AGA with tumor diseases, AH, IHD, COPD, and ARD.

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